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ORIGINAL ARTICLE

ISLAMIC ASSESSMENT OF MODES OF INVESTIGATION BY THE ECONOMIC AND FINANCIAL CRIMES COMMISSION (EFCC) IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Corruption is a worldwide phenomenon, it is the single most important social problem in Nigeria today. To combat it, the Nigerian government has set up various bodies, including the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC). Despite this effort, one may observe that new forms of corrupt practices are developed by perpetrators, as evident in daily news media with dismay and continue to grow worse. This shows that the only solution to corruption is to adhere to Allah's laws and avoid corruption in its totality. Corruption is perhaps, the only reason why nothing seems to be working correctly in the country. It is given the gravity of corruption that this paper assesses the modes of investigation of corrupt officials by EFCC (an anti-graft agency saddled with the responsibility of investigating financial and economic criminals for onward prosecution of such offenders in a court of justice) from an Islamic perspective. This paper assesses the modes of concordance of the laws/procedures of EFCC with that of Islam in the war against corruption. The methodology used is the survey method where data were collected from both primary and secondary sources. The paper discovered that the procedures of operation in EFCC differ from Islam; however, there are some of the laws of the Commission that conform to Islamic Law. The paper, recommends the application of spiritual, economic, social and political strategies through justice and fair play for the eradication of corruption in the country. Also, the anti-graft agencies should undertake a serious and thorough investigation before arraigning an accused person to court. They should also operate on a neutral ground based on uprightness, total commitment, and a sense of responsibility if the desired goal is to be achieved.

Keywords: Islam, Assessment, Investigation, Corruption, Financial Crime, Identifying, Justice.

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INTRODUCTION

The problem of corruption attracted the attention of scholars, activists, international organizations and the general public for a very long time. It has received extensive attention from both policymakers and scholars in contemporary societies. Even though the problem is not new in Nigeria, it has reached unprecedented proportions in recent years (Abdulkareem 1). It cuts across nations, cultures, races and organizations. Corruption is undoubtedly one of the greatest challenges of our time, a challenge that is not only leading to impoverishment and loss of lives but also threatening the stability of societies. It has been argued by social scientists that one of the major obstacles against the development of poor countries is corruption.

Corruption is globally endemic. It is threatening world peace, progress and human survival as it continues to manifest in several ways and dimensions. The progression of corruption as one of the world-leading problems continues unabated. Several attempts have been made by social scientists to explain the phenomenon of corruption and its control without success. Humanity is today ravaged by corruption and so far, all attempts by social scientists, critics and people of other opinions and disciplines to stamp out the menace posed by corruption have not produced desired results. Though some analysts tend to suggest that developed countries are less prone to corruption than developing countries, this position cannot be emphatically defended as past experiences and events proved otherwise (Abdulkareem 1).

Corruption does not dispose itself to any colouration in the forms of religious denominations, political system, age or gender. It is found in political, social, religious and economic systems. Every country suffers one form of Corruption or the other (Lipset and Gabriel). The Glorious Qur'ān affirms its worldwide phenomenal dimension when it reads:

Corruption has appeared on land and sea because of (the meed) that the hands of men have earned, that (God) may give them a taste of some of their deeds: so that they may turn back (from Evil) (Q 30:41).

Nigeria, being the most populated country in Africa, has been ranked high in corruption by Transparency International Index and other notable Organizations that checkmate the level of corrupt practices in many countries. It does not tell well of Nigeria as a country. This high corruption ranking has been affecting Nigerians that travelled to foreign countries as host communities have the perception that since the country is marked corrupt, almost all of them (Nigerians) have a share in the practice. Nigerians are therefore ridiculed or looked down upon with disdain or lack of respect. This development is embarrassing to the citizenry.

Transparency International carried out some studies across the globe and came up with their findings thus: in February 2018, Nigeria was ranked 148 out of 180 countries, scoring 28 out of 100 maximum points. Thus, Nigeria was the 32nd most corrupt nation in the world. In fact, in West Africa, Nigeria is the second most corrupt country out of 17 countries, leaving only Guinea Bissau behind. This

confirms that grand corruption; political corruption, nepotism, favouritism and bribery persist at all levels and in all sectors of the country.

In Nigeria, there are two laws enacted in a bid to fight corruption. These are the Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC) Act 2000 and the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (Establishment) Act 2004 respectively. Section 2 of the ICPC Act defines corruption to include, bribery, fraud and other related offences while the EFCC has powers to investigate and prosecute offences such as advance fee fraud, money laundering, counterfeiting, illegal funds transfers, futures and market fraud, fraudulent encashment of negotiable instruments, fraudulent diversion of funds, computer fraud, contract scam, forgery of financial instruments and issuance of dud cheque (2-5).

From the Islamic law perspective, however, corruption is defined as a spiritual or moral impurity or deviation from an ideal. According to Islamic teaching, any action of mankind that flout justice or rule of law whether, at home, place of work, learning institutions, social or political gathering are an act of corruption (Shehu5). It covers a wide range of illegal practices which undermine fear of Allah, morality, decency, social justice, and good governance, rule of law, harmony, peace, progress and development. Islamic law, therefore, looks at corruption from a moral and ethical angle and strongly offers a universally comprehensible blueprint for human behaviour which revolves around social justice, equitable distribution of wealth, provision of necessities of life and the protection of the weak against economic exploitation by the strong (Mamoun 4).

It is important to consider the various manifestations of corruption which come in different dimensions; ranging from bribery, diversion of public funds, tax evasions, selling justice for money, sales and leakage of examination questions, lecturers selling marks for sexual favours, police extortion of motorists, favouritism in bidding process and appointments, admissions into higher institutions of learning through connections, over-invoicing and falsification of documents, immigration officers collecting money to issue passports, money laundering, forgery and counterfeiting, illegal trade in arms, misappropriation and misuse of public funds, violation of official oath, political patronage, divide and rule techniques and looting of public funds (El-Rufai 2).

Mode of identifying corrupt officials by EFCC

Economic and Financial Crime Commission EFCC by the Act which established it has the mandate to identify investigate and institute legal action against any person or group of persons at the law court. The following are the means of investigating corrupt officials by the EFCC:

- 1. Through petition; the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission EFCC identifies corrupt officials through petition duly signed by an individual or group of persons from ministries, parastatal or company indicting an official or citizen. When this report is received it investigates the genuineness of the petition and invites the accused person for interrogation. When it is proved beyond a reasonable doubt, the commission will arraign the accused to court for judgments.*

In Islamic criminal law, offences are reported and verified before any legal action is taken. In the Glorious Qur'ān Allāh says:

O you who believe! If a rebellious evil person comes to you with news, verify it, lest you harm people in ignorance, and afterwards, you become regretful to what you have done. And know that, among you, there is the Messenger of Allāh (SAW). If he were to obey you (i.e. follow your opinions and desires) in much of the matter, you would surely be in trouble, but Allāh has endeared the Faith to you and has beautified it in your hearts, and has made disbelief, wickedness and disobedience (to Allāh and His Messenger SAW) hateful to you. These! They are the rightly guided ones, O you who believe! Avoid many suspicions, indeed some suspicions are sins. And spy not, neither backbite one another. Would one of you like to eat the flesh of his dead brother? You would hate it (so hate backbiting). And fear Allāh. Verily, Allāh is the One Who accepts repentance, Most Merciful. O mankind! We have created you from a male and a female, and made you into nations and tribes, that you may know one another. Verily, the most honourable of you with Allāh is that (believer) who has At-Taqwa [i.e. one of the Muttaqûn (pious - see V.2:2). Verily, Allāh is All-Knowing, All-Aware. (Q49-6-13).

From the above Qur'ānic verses it is clear that verifying any given information is a requirement for ascertaining the authenticity or otherwise of any report or petition. Islamic criminal law, admit one's fault when it becomes clear that he/she gets involved in any unlawful act not necessarily through a petition by other citizens. Prophet Muḥammad (SAW) issued a stern warning against passing on all that one hears:

Narrated by al-Mughīrah ibn Shu'bah (RA) said: The Prophet (SAW) says:

Allāh has forbidden you to disobey your mothers, to bury your daughters to not pay the rights of others and to beg from others. And He alive, dislike dislikes gossip for you, asking too many questions, and wasting money. (Bukhari, 2231).

The above verse and *Hadith* of the Prophet (SAW) indicated that one is not expected to write or report one whose source is undisclosed to him, until when it was proved beyond a reasonable doubt.

2. Through report/complaint; EFCC also identifies corrupt persons by report/complaint through somebody who has been cheated. In this case, Islam allowed people to lodge their complaints either as an individual, state, local government, ministry, commission, parastatal to seek redress where it is wronged. The noble Qur'ān has condemned cheating and the people who do it and warned them of bad consequences.

Similarly, Prophet (SAW) cautioned Muslims against cheating and issued a warning to the one who does this.

Narrated AbūHurayrah: The Messenger of Allāh (SAW) happened to pass by a heap of eatables (corn). He thrust his hand in that (heap) and his fingers were moistened. He said to the owner of the heap of eatable (corn):

What is this? Messenger of Allah, these have been drenched by rainfall. He (the Prophet) remarked: Why did you not place this (the drenched part of the heap) over other eatables so that the people could see it? He who deceives, is not of me (is not my follower) (Muslim 1: 0183).

We need desperately to instil this message in our hearts so that we might stir the conscience and be aware that Allāh is watching all that we do, without the need for any human supervisor.

3. *When one is living above his/her income (inference); the Economic and Financial Crime Commission investigates people who are living above their income. In Islamic criminal law, there is an established rule that: suspicions must be considered. living beyond one's income is suspicious, such an act could be reported to the appropriate body. For example, the case of a non-married pregnant girl, to the Malikiyah school of thought, is a valid proof of Zina (fornication) and she should be reported to a judge (Al-Zurqaani vol. 4, 150). If truly it was a case of fornication that resulted in pregnancy, she will be subjected to ḥadd punishment as stated in the Qurʾān:*

The woman and the man guilty of illegal sexual intercourse, flog each of them with a hundred stripes. Let not pity withhold you in their case, in a punishment prescribed by Allāh, if you believe in Allāh and the Last Day. And let a party of the believers witness their punishment. (This punishment is for unmarried persons guilty of the above crime but if married persons commit it, the punishment is to stone them to death, according to Allāh's Law) (Q24:2).

4. *Through whistle blowing; whistle blowing is the fourth method of identifying corrupt officials by EFCC. A whistleblower is a person who exposes any kind of information or activity that is deemed illegal, unethical, or not correct within an organization that is either private or public (Wim 12). Mr Ibrahim Magu the acting chairman of EFCC stated that the commission has recovered about N17billion for the Federal Government of Nigeria through the whistle-blowing policy introduced by the Government in December 2017.*

This method may be accepted by Islam if situated within the horizon of business ethics to promote truth and save society from being harmed. These conventional motives of whistleblowing may be similar to the Islamic general motives which are encoded on ethics. It is very important to know that Islam is a religion that teaches good ethics.

One may consider whistleblowing mandatory duty on a Muslim if he/she looks at it from the point of enjoining right and forbidding wrongdoing (*al-ḥamr bi-*

ma'rūf) wa nahy 'annil Munkar. Whistleblowing according to Nāsīr is one of the three stages of *īmān*, faith as narrated from Abi Saidul Khudri (R.A): the Prophet (SAW) said:

I heard the Messenger of Allah (SAW) say, "Whosoever of you sees an evil, let him change it with his hand; and if he is not able to do so, then [let him change it] with his tongue; and if he is not able to do so, then with his heart and that is the weakest degree of faith (Muslim).

From the above *hadīth*, we can deduce that reporting any illegal activity to the appropriate body may be regarded as Whistle blowing. All these can be justified from the perspective of Islamic Law.

Modes of Investigation by the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC)

After identifying corrupt officials, the Commission monitors/her movement, phone calls, transactions in banks through Bank Verification Number (BVN) and goes further to invite him/her and forward verified reports to the responsible investigation unit of the commissions.

One of the major impediments of EFCC right from on set is its inability to carry out a proper and thorough investigation before embarking on the arrest. There are some calls by Nigerians to EFCC to carry out a proper investigation before any arrest. The Commission has been asked to desist from illegal arrests and detention of innocent persons based on fictitious petitions until it has conducted thorough investigations to establish the authenticity or otherwise of accusations. The call was made by the young Professionals Alliance for Change (PAC) based in the Delta State of Nigeria after the arrest and detention of the former Managing director of the Petroleum Products Pricing and Marketing Company, Mrs Esther Ogbue-Nnamdi by the EFCC, she was later released because her arrest was illegal, unacceptable and at variance with both the Commission's Act and the 1999 Constitution as amended (This Day Newspaper). This is an issue which the Commission always denies. According to the acting Chairman of EFCC, Mr Ibrahim Magu the Commission usually investigates financial crimes in line with international best practices; before inviting the accused persons. The Commission invites the accused only after a lot of background checks and whenever the accused arrives the Commission only asks him/her to corroborate the findings after which it grants bail to suspect(s). It is then left to the suspect to meet the conditions attached to the bail (Ugwuanyi 3).

After inviting the accused persons, the Commission interrogates him/her by presenting exhibits which may include a statement of bank account by way of income and expenditure and a list of some of his/her assets.

The next step after inviting the suspect is for the Commission to ask the suspect to write his/her statement and file in Assets declaration form (see Appendix A) which is usually written in the presence of either his/her lawyer,

close relative or friend. According to the Act, it is an offence punishable by up to a maximum of 5 years imprisonment to hide any information. After getting his/her statement the Commission would decide whether to release the suspect on condition of bail or to detain him. When that is decided based on the circumstance, if the decision is to detain the suspect, the Commission must go to court of law and obtain the detain warrant which usually lasts for either 24 or 48 hours before which the suspect must be arraigned before a court of appropriate jurisdiction for trial.

When a suspect is invited to the Commission but refuses to honour the invitation, the Commission orders for his/her arrest. Upon accepting the invitation or arrest, he/she will be ordered to write a statement wherein he/she is expected to list all his/her belongings, by EFCC Act. After that, the Commission, sometimes orders for the freezing of the accused bank account. (See Appendix B).

Two Qur'anic historical antecedents are found useful in carrying out this work. These are *Iffk* (slandering lie) about 'Ā'ishah (RA), Şafwān and 'Abdullāh Ibn 'Ubayy on one hand, and Bilqīs the Queen of Saba'i (Yemen) on the other, with Hud-Huda and Prophet Sulaimān (AS). The former is disastrous and scandalous while the latter example is high, informative and worthy of emulation for EFCC to acquire the best skills for proper investigation. While the latter example is highly informative. *Hud-Huda* reported to Prophet Sulaimān an incident which the Glorious Qur'an records:

I found a woman ruling over them, and she has been given all things that could be possessed by any ruler on the earth, and she has a great throne. I found her and her people worshipping the sun instead of Allāh, and Shaiṭān (Satan) has made their deeds fair-seeming to them, and has barred them from (Allāh's) Way, so they have no guidance," Al-L (this word has two interpretations) (a) As Shaiṭān (Satan) has barred them from Allāh's Way] so that they do not worship (prostrate before) Allāh, or (b) So that they may worship (prostrate before) Allāh, Who brings to light what is hidden in the heavens and the earth, and knows what you conceal and what you reveal. (Tafsīr Aṭ-Ṭabarī, Vol. 19, 149).

Allāh, *Lā ilāha illa Huwa* (none has the right to be worshipped but He), the Lord of the Supreme Throne!

Sulaimān (Solomon) said: "We shall see whether you speak the truth or you are (one) of the liars.

Go you with this letter of mine, and deliver it to them, then draw back from them, and see what (answer) they return.

She said: "O chiefs! Verily! Here is delivered to me a noble letter, Verily! It is from Sulaimān (Solomon), and verily! It (reads): In the Name of Allāh, the Most Beneficent, the Most Merciful;
(Q27: 23-30)

The content of the verses can serve as a lesson to EFCC in its facts' finding, intelligence gathering and dissemination of factual information appropriately to the public with a full sense of fairness and objectivity. The historical antecedent is also very relevant to this paper as it serves as a laboratory for every successful investigation officer in the Commission. As Hud-Huda revealed the information to Prophet Sulaiman (AS), his first step was to commence an investigation to verify how factual the news is before considering the next line of action. So, EFCC as a Commission is not expected to rush into the arrest of any person who has been petitioned against until proper investigation is carried out so as to avoid scandalous lies which may soil the Commission. (Al- Ajiliy Vol. V. 441).

On the contrary was the narration of *Ifk* (slandering lie) against 'Ā'ishah (RA) by Safwan and 'Abdullah ibn 'Ubayy, the Qur'an reads:

Verily! Those who brought forth the slander (against 'Ā'ishah (RA) (the wife of the Prophet SAW) are a group among you. Consider it not a bad thing for you. Nay, it is good for you. Unto every man among them will be paid that which he had earned of the sin, and as for him among them who had the greater share therein, his will be a great torment.

Why then, did not the believers, men and women, when you heard it (the slander) think good of their own people and say: "This (charge) is an obvious lie?

Why did they not produce four witnesses? Since they (the slanderers) have not produced witnesses! Then with Allah, they are the liars.

Had it not been for the Grace of Allah and His Mercy unto you in this world and in the Hereafter, a great torment would have touched you for that whereof you had spoken.

When you were propagating it with your tongues, and uttering with your mouths that whereof you had no knowledge, you counted it a little thing, while with Allah it was very great.

And why did you not, when you heard it, say? "It is not right for us to speak of this. Glory be to You (O Allāh) this is a great lie."

Allāh forbids you from it and warns you not to repeat the like of it forever if you are believers.

And Allah makes the Ayat (proofs, evidence, verses, lessons, signs, revelations, etc.) plain to you, and Allah is All-Knowing, All-Wise. (Q24:11-18.

The above verses narrate the false crime story against 'Ā'ishah (RA) the wife of the Prophet (SAW) that was deliberately initiated and spread by 'Abdullah ibn 'Ubayy (the leader of hypocrites) in the town of Madīnah and Šafwan against 'Ā'ishah (RA) (Ibn Kathīr, Vol. III).

It is not permissible in Islam to accuse any man or woman of slanderous lie act (i.e. *Zina*) without proof of four witnesses with good character, confession

(Zina). Whoever does that has committed a major sin and shall be punished for the act, which is eighty lashes on his back, and his testimony is never to be accepted in the future, and he is not to be described as being of good character, rather he is to be labelled as a *fāsiq* (evildoer). Sex offences would be severely punished, but the strictest evidence should be required, and false slanders are also worthy of punishment.

This story can serve as a corrective and proper guide for investigation by EFCC in approaching and addressing issues brought or reported to the Commission in any form. In respect of this

CONCLUSION

The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) is a law enforcement agency in Nigeria that is charged with the responsibility of identifying, investigating and arraigning suspects of financial crimes such as advance fee fraud (419) money laundering, counterfeiting, illegal charges transfers, future market fraud, fraudulent encashment of negotiable instruments, computer credit card frauds, counteract scam etc to the court of law.

The paper observed that the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) that fights corruption in Nigeria have a lot to learn from the historical antecedents emanating from *lfa* (slanderous lie) against 'Āishah (RA) and intelligence gathering on Prophet Sulaiman on Bilqis the queen of Saba' (Yemen) in carrying out their official duty. So as not to be guilty of slander and defamation of character. Many Nigerians believe that the Commission does not carry out the arrest and publish it in the newspaper before investigating an allegation. The paper recommends the application of economic, social and political strategies through the criminal justice and fair play, reformation of the spiritual spheres and ensuring that accused persons are punished for the offences committed in order to minimize corruption to the barest level in the country. Also, the anti-graft agencies should be allowed to operate on a neutral ground-based on uprightness, total commitment, and a sense of responsibility, if the desired result is to be achieved.

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APPENDIX A SCHEDULE

CONFIDENTIAL FORM A

ECONOMIC AND FINANCIAL CRIMES COMMISSION ACT 2004

DECLARATION OF ASSETS FORM

To be completed in TRIPLICATE and in BLOCK LETTERS or typed.

All available information should be included

Important: It is an offence punishable by up to a maximum of 5 years imprisonment under the Act to

- (A) (i) Knowingly fail to make full disclosure of your assets and liabilities
(ii) Knowingly make a declaration that is false
(iii) Fail, neglect or refuse to make a declaration or furnish any information required

(B) (i) Each item is to be completed. If it does not apply, the person affected must write 'nil' or 'none' in the space. Where necessary, an extra sheet or sheets may be used and attached to this form by the person affected.

- ii. Buildings:
- iii. Other property, (if any).

25. Property outside Nigeria in which any child of yours is interested in giving date when acquired-

- i. Land:
- ii. Buildings
- iii. Other property, (if any).

26. Names of other dependent relatives:

27. Estate in which you are interested as trustee or beneficially interested (Name of deceased or trustee).

28. Property held by any person on your behalf- (in or outside Nigeria)

- i. Cash in hand;
- ii. Cash at bank;
- iii. Land:
- iv. Buildings
- v. Other Properties

If outside Nigeria, insert names of countries and banks.....

.....
 Signature of Accused
 Person

.....
Signature and Address of Witness

**Appendix B
FORM B
FREEZING ORDER**

(This form may be amended according to circumstances)

1. To the Manager

.....
(Here insert name and branch of bank)

Under the authority conferred on me by section 33 of the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission Act, you are hereby ordered

(a) to supply the following information relating to the under mentioned accounts, that is to say

.....
(Here set out the information required in respect of named accounts)

(b) to produce the books and documents relating to the under mentioned

accounts, that is to say

.....
(Here set out the books and documents to be produced in respect of the named accounts)

(c) To stop all Outward payments, operations or transactions (including bills of exchange) as far as possible in the ordinary course of banking in respect of the following accounts:

.....
(Here indicate the accounts)

2. This order shall remain in force until revoked

DATED atthis..... day of 20.....

Chairman/Authorized Officer

